

Assessing the suitability of forensic authorship analysis methodologies for speech data

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Feature levels in Auditory/Acoustic FSC

- Different types of features analysed in Auditory/Acoustic FSC analysis (Gold and French, 2011: 301-302).
 - **Segmental features** (vowels and consonants)
 - **Suprasegmental features** (F0, articulation rate, rhythmic properties of speech)
 - **“Higher order linguistic features”** (discourse or conversational patterns, grammar, lexis, syntax, morphology)
 - **Non-linguistic features** (pausing, breathing, throat clearing, laughter)

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Analysing 'text-based' features in speech

- Recent work has focussed on the application of methods from authorship analysis to speech data.
- Conversion process required from speech into writing. A **transcript** of the data is therefore needed - becoming increasingly accessible thanks to automatic transcription systems?
- Potentially useful in certain types of speaker comparison cases, but currently unclear as to the best way to implement methods in FSC.

Analysing ‘text-based’ features in speech

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Frequent-words analysis for forensic speaker comparison

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Highlights

- Frequent-words analysis has speaker-discriminatory power.
- Percentile rank is a simple but effective way to take typicality/rarity into account, in combination with the similarity of the recordings.
- A likelihood ratio system based on the transcription of spontaneous speech is presented.

“We showed that frequent-words analysis has speaker-discriminatory power. Our method is designed to work in a forensic setting, where little reference material may be available and results for any specific speech fragment should be explained and interpreted in court.”

(Sergidou et al., 2023)

Analysing ‘text-based’ features in speech

“The findings of this study add to the emerging literature (Sergidou et al., 2023) which suggests that lexico-grammatical elements could be analysed as a speaker-discriminatory feature in FSC.

However, the study also highlights that the use of these features should be approached with caution, as variation for some features was greatly impacted by discourse type.”

(Visser, 2024; Visser et al., forthcoming)

Analysing ‘text-based’ features in speech

“It is remarkable that applying authorship analysis methods to spoken data has only caught research attention very recently – this is likely a result of the distance that has traditionally existed between forensic linguistics and forensic speech science.”

(Brown, Nini and Kirchhübel, 2024)

Authorship analysis methods

Authorship verification

vs

Same speaker or not?

Burrows' Delta

Word	NORM	author 1	author 2	NORM – author 1	NORM – author 2
a	3%	2.8%	3.1%	- 1	+ 1
an	4%	3.9%	4.1%	- 0.5	+ 0.5
all	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0	0
also	0.1%	0%	3%	- 0.1	+ 3
some	0.001%	0.0001%	0.0002%	- 0.001	- 0.001
upon	0.1%	3%	0%	+ 4	- 4

Cosine Delta

Most frequent 50 words

The cat sat on the mat and the dog sat on the chair.

N-gram tracing

B

Q text

N-gram tracing

B

Q text

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

A

$4/5 = 80\%$

B

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

word 2-grams

Phi coefficient

Content masking

The cat sat on the mat and the dog sat on the chair.

The * * on the * and the * * on the * .

The N V on the N and the N V on the N .

Parts of Speech tags

Experiment 1

Experiment 1

- Exploring the combination of segmental and “higher-order” features.
- Reminder: different types of features analysed in Auditory/Acoustic FSC analysis (Gold and French, 2011: 301-302).
 - **Segmental features** (vowels and consonants)
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Feature levels in FSC

- Different types of features analysed in Auditory/Acoustic FSC analysis (Gold and French, 2011: 301-302).

- **Segmental features** (vowels and consonants)

- **Suprasegmental features** (F0, articulation rate, rhythmic properties of speech)

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Is there a way of directly combining these two types of features in an analysis? And is this even worth doing?

Experiment 1

- Focus on **filled pauses (FPs)**. Previous acoustic-phonetic work on this feature by Hughes et al. (2016: 1), which described FPs as having “*excellent potential as variables in forensic voice comparison cases*”.
- The authors also highlight that “*discourse structure also affects the frequency and type of FP used*” (Hughes et al., 2016: 3), but their analysis focussed on “*when they [FPs] occur in talk, irrespective of where they occur*” (Hughes et al., 2016: 6).
- **Research question:** Does the combination of phonetically transcribed FP plus “higher-level” linguistic information provide useful speaker-discriminatory power?
- **Data:** Tested using West Yorkshire Regional English Database (WYRED) (Gold et al., 2018). 30 speakers used in our pilot project. Only **Task 1 (Mock Police interview)** and **Task 2 (Telephone conversation with accomplice)**.

Experiment 1

#	Transcription	Realisation
1	“eh”	FP with a mid-central or fronter/raised vowel realisation, such as [ɜ:], [ɛ:] or [e:]
2	“ah”	FP with a more open vowel quality realisation, around [a:] or [ɛ:]
3	“ehm”	FP as in (1) plus a bilabial nasal [m]
4	“ahm”	FP as in (2), plus a bilabial nasal [m]
5	“uh”	Vocalic hesitation marker with a quality that is different to those described in (1) and (2)
6	“uhm”	Vocalic hesitation marker with a quality that is different to those described in (1) and (2), plus a bilabial nasal [m]
7	“mm”	Hesitation marker containing only a nasal

Hesitations

eh ah ehm ahm ur um mm

No hesitations

vs

Only hesitations

vs

Both

Hesitations only word 2-grams

eh_i

P_eh

know_eh

eh_he

P_ah

ah_yeah

N_ah

ah_i

N_eh

eh_just

Experiment 2

Combining text-based and phonetic information

- “I go up the A40 to Carter Road” – Text level

Feature	Realisation
GOAT vowel	[ɔ] - go (1 sec) [e:] - road (2 sec)
STRUT vowel	[ʊ] - up (1 sec)
START vowel	[a:] - Carter (2 sec)
happY vowel	[ɛ] - forty (1 sec)
Word-initial /ð/	[d̪] - the (1 sec)
Intervocalic /t/	[ʔ] - forty (1 sec), Carter (2 sec)

Experiment 2

- Hughes (2014) - more difficult for LR frameworks to deal with discrete data than continuous acoustic measures.
- Combining this discrete consonant phonetic variability with 'higher-order' linguistic features.
- More variation captured, greater discriminatory power? Ability to capture consonant variation within the LR framework?
- Balance between usefulness and overall practicality?

Experiment 2

Variable	Realisations
-ing suffix	[ɪŋ]
	[ɪn]
<hr/>	
Intervocalic word-medial /t/	[t]
	[ʔ]
	[r]
<hr/>	
Syllable-initial (voiceless) th-fronting/stopping	[θ]
	[f]
	[t]
<hr/>	
Syllable-initial /l/	[l]
	[lʲ]

Experiment 2

Variable	Phonetic realisation	Orthographic coding
-ing suffix	[ɪŋ]	YNG
	[ɪn]	YN

These are then re-integrated back into the transcript - adding phonetic information

Cosine Delta (Only phonetic information)

$C_{llr} = 0.71$

EER = 21

Tippet plot

Cosine Delta (Phonetic information + function words)

$C_{llr} = 0.63$

EER = 16

Tippet plot

Grammar as a Behavioral Biometric: Using Cognitively Motivated Grammar Models for Authorship Verification

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$C_{llr} = 0.26$

EER = 3.6

Tippet plot

Where next?

- Thinking about areas or types of comparisons where this analysis could prove either more or less useful?
- Exploring different types of analysis methods used in authorship analysis?
- Trying methods on data which is different to DyViS or WYRED?
- More work on cross-genre or cross-discourse types?
- Others..?

Thank you!

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